

Academic Misconduct and the Perception-Reality Gap: Evidence from China and Roles for Scientometrics

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Abstract

This study examines the critical gap between researchers' perceptions of academic misconduct and objective bibliometric realities. Drawing on the AMEND retracted-paper database and a survey of 1,005 Chinese researchers and administrators, we identify five core misalignments: the mismatch between perceived scale and actual prevalence, the stereotype of discipline-specific fraud, the conflation of honest error with misconduct, the persistence of "zombie papers," and the misplaced responsibility regarding systemic challenges. To address this gap, we position scientometricians as essential boundary-spanners in research integrity governance. We outline four active roles for the scientometric community: building monitoring infrastructure, issuing early fire alarms, patrolling evaluation metrics, and brokering knowledge across diverse stakeholders. This approach translates diagnostic evidence into actionable governance tools.

Keywords: Research integrity; Academic misconduct; Perception-reality gap; Collaborative governance; Scientometric tools

1. Introduction

Research integrity and the governance of academic misconduct have become a central focus of global science. However, as institutions move from awareness to action, they struggle to accurately assess the true scope of the problem: what is the current status of misconduct, and how does it align with the perception of the research community? Identifying the gap between perception and reality is critical, as it determines whether governance succeeds or falters. Before deciding on a course of action, we must determine our current position. If the perceived crisis is driven by information silos, the primary task is to correct cognitive biases through evidence-based communication (Jamieson, 2018). If this perception reflects systemic vulnerabilities that existing metrics fail to capture, the priority must shift to direct intervention and technical safeguards (Else & Van Noorden, 2021). Without clarifying this relationship, governance efforts risk being either reactive and over-punitive or dangerously insufficient.

This paper addresses this challenge by examining the empirical evidence of misconduct in comparison to scientific community perceptions. Building on this analysis, we move beyond theoretical debates to focus on practical strategies. We suggest that scientometricians are uniquely positioned to bridge these gaps. Specifically, we present four active roles for the scientometric community: building monitoring infrastructure, issuing early fire alarms, patrolling evaluation metrics, and acting as knowledge intermediaries. By fulfilling these roles, scientometricians can

translate diagnostic evidence into actionable governance tools.

2. Data and Methods

This study integrates two primary data sources to cross-examine objective bibliometric records against subjective researcher perceptions. The empirical data analyzed in this study are derived from a companion report (Tong et al., 2024). While the report provides extensive baseline statistics, this paper focuses specifically on the perception-reality gap and the corresponding governance roles.

- **Bibliometric data.** To measure the objective reality of misconduct, we utilized the 2024 version of the AMEND platform (Li et al., 2024). AMEND aggregates retraction and expression-of-concern records from three distinct channels: official journal notices, post-publication peer commentary, and government investigation announcements. Our primary analysis focuses on a 20-year period from 2003 to 2022. However, to plot a complete temporal trajectory for specific phenomena, such as overall growth trends and the persistence of post-retraction citations, we expanded the observation window from 1980 to 2023. The resulting dataset contains 26,388 retracted papers, of which 21,826 represent confirmed cases of misconduct. To analyze disciplinary distribution, we mapped these papers using a combination of Web of Science Citation Topics¹ and the five major field classifications developed by CWTS².
- **Questionnaire data.** To capture subjective perception, we conducted a questionnaire survey distributed through a professional academic WeChat public account. We collected 1,005 valid responses from the Chinese research community. The survey evaluated how researchers perceive the prevalence of misconduct, their understanding of retraction mechanisms, their daily citation verification habits, and their views on governance responsibilities.

3. Findings

3.1. *The mismatch between scale and perception*

Our data shows that the number of identified misconduct papers rose from 1,949 in 2020 to 5,833 in 2022 (see Figure 1). Despite this sharp increase, confirmed misconduct remains rare in relative terms, accounting for 0.04% to 0.16% of total research output across major fields (see Table 1).

¹ <https://clarivate.com/academia-government/blog/introducing-citation-topics/>

² <https://traditional.leidenranking.com/information/fields>

Figure 1. Number of academic misconduct papers worldwide from 1980 to 2022. Reproduced from Tong et al. (2024)

Note: the years shown in the figure indicate when the papers were published.

Table 1. Number and proportion of misconduct papers across various fields (2003-2022)

Research field	Number of misconduct papers	Misconduct rate (%)
Biomedical and health sciences	10951	0.10
Mathematics and computer science	3683	0.16
Physical sciences and engineering	3435	0.04
Social sciences and humanities	1551	0.08
Life and earth sciences	1343	0.03

Note: Misconduct rate (%) represents the percentage of misconduct papers relative to total research output.

In contrast, our survey result regarding the question of “How severe do you consider research integrity violations in your own field?” shows a profound psychological gap. More than 12% of researchers reported a serious lack of trust in their field, and only 16% viewed the situation as manageable (see Table 2).

Table 2. Distribution of perceived severity ratings

Score	n	%	Mean	SD
1 (Almost nonexistent)	165	16.4	2.79	1.23
2	270	26.9		
3	305	30.3		
4	142	14.1		
5 (Very severe)	123	12.2		

Note: 1 = Almost nonexistent, 5 = Very severe

Three factors likely drive this mismatch. First, high-profile academic scandals attract massive public and academic attention (Jamieson, 2018). This creates an inflated illusion of widespread

fraud, a phenomenon known as availability bias. Second, researchers often witness or personally engaged in questionable practices. These everyday behaviors directly erode local trust but rarely result in formal retractions or appear in bibliometric data (John et al., 2012). Third, official databases only record detected offenses. The current volume of retracted papers may simply be the tip of the iceberg (Fanelli, 2009).

This perception gap requires immediate attention because it presents two opposing risks for integrity governance. If institutions overreact based on heightened anxieties, they may create a punitive environment that breeds unnecessary panic and discourages honest self-correction. Conversely, if institutions underreact by trusting only the low official metrics, they will fail to address the unmeasured reality of everyday misconduct and allow systemic vulnerabilities to grow unchecked.

3.2. The stereotype of discipline-specific misconduct

A prevailing stereotype, clearly reflected in our survey data regarding the question of “Which disciplines do you consider the 'hardest hit' by research integrity violations?”, suggests that academic misconduct is primarily a biomedical problem (Table 3). Our empirical mapping of retracted papers from 2003 to 2022 directly contradicts this assumption (Figure 2).

Table 3. Top 5 disciplines ranked by perceived integrity violation severity

Rank	Discipline	n	%
1	Medicine	622	61.9
2	Biology	454	45.2
3	Materials Science	266	26.5
4	Social Sciences	196	19.5
5	Chemistry	180	17.9

Figure 2. Science map of academic misconduct papers across all fields (2003-2022). Reproduced from Tong et al. (2024)

Note: The color of each circle represents the corresponding field, and the area of the circle

indicates the number of academic misconduct papers in each research topic.

The largest number of retractions does occur in the biomedical and health sciences. This high concentration is partly due to the massive publication volume and intense public scrutiny of health research. However, the data reveals substantial clusters of misconduct across all five major scientific fields.

These findings indicate that academic misconduct is not isolated to any single discipline. The perception of a purely biomedical crisis is a dangerous stereotype because it creates a false sense of security in other research areas. Therefore, while vigilance must be universal across all scientific fields, governance strategies cannot be one-size-fits-all. Institutions must expand their oversight to eliminate disciplinary blind spots, but specific interventions must be explicitly tailored to the distinct problem patterns and research contexts of each field.

3.3. Misconduct vs. honest error

Not all retractions indicate misconduct. Our data in Figure 3 shows that approximately 16% of retractions over the past two decades resulted from honest errors, such as analytical mistakes or contaminated samples. However, the survey reveals a widespread conflation of error and fraud among researchers. Specifically, 53.3% of respondents lack an understanding of the exact reasons behind retractions (see Table 4).

Figure 3. Distribution of reasons for retraction (2003-2022). Reproduced from Tong et al. (2024)

Table 4. Distribution of awareness comprehensiveness

Number of Causes Selected	n	%	Interpretation
Selected 3 of 3 options	469	46.7	Complete
Selected 2 of 3 options	378	37.6	Incomplete
Selected 1 of 3 options	158	15.7	Incomplete

Note: Respondents who selected all three options are classified as having comprehensive awareness of retraction causes; those who selected fewer than three are classified as having incomplete awareness.

This potential misunderstanding may create a dangerous result. When the research community fails to distinguish genuine mistakes from academic fraud, researchers are actively discouraged from correcting their own work. Treating all retractions as misconduct fosters a climate of fear, exacerbating the reality that retractions still unwittingly punish all who take part (Couzin-Frankel, 2016).

3.4. The “zombie paper” phenomenon

Retracted publications often survive as "zombie papers" that continue to accumulate citations as valid research (Brainard, 2022; Joëts & Mignon, 2026). Analysis of post-retraction citation patterns in the companion project report reveals a prolonged lifespan for these invalidated works (Tong et al., 2024), here we list 3 sample retracted misconduct papers in Figure 4. Most critically, citing authors frequently adopt these retracted papers as methodological foundations, propagating questionable knowledge into subsequent research and practical education (Schneider et al., 2020).

Figure 4. Citations of three retracted misconduct papers before and after retraction. Reproduced from Tong et al. (2024)

Note: Points denote three retracted publications due to misconduct. Colors distinguish individual papers. The legend specifies the research topic, journal of publication, publication year, and retraction year for each case.

Our survey data regarding the question of “Do you check the retraction status of the references you cite?” identifies the operational gap driving this phenomenon. Exactly 42.5% of researchers admit they do not verify the retraction status of their references (see Table 5). This blind spot highlights a dual imperative: cultivating responsible citation habits and enhancing the digital infrastructure of academic publishing. While current reference management tools offer foundational support, their automated warning mechanisms require further integration and strengthening to systematically intercept retracted content.

Table 5. Distribution of reference retraction checking behavior

Response	n	%
Check all references	296	29.5
Check key references only	282	28.1
Do not check	427	42.5

3.5. Systemic challenges and misplaced responsibility

As shown in Figure 5, the breakdown of misconduct types reveals that fraud permeates every stage of the knowledge production cycle. First, within the research and writing process, traditional violations such as duplication (27%), plagiarism (10%), falsification (7%) and fabrication (6%) remain prevalent. Second, during the publication and review phase, structural weaknesses are heavily exploited, predominantly through fake peer review (47%). Third, the emergence of paper mills (10%) signifies a severe shift toward organized, industrialized fraud.

Figure 5. Distribution of issues related to academic misconduct papers (2003-2022). Reproduced from Tong et al. (2024)

However, our survey reveals a significant displacement of responsibility (question of “*How effective do you consider the following measures for strengthening research integrity?*”). While the empirical data demands a collaborative defense, researchers often shift the burden of governance to external parties. As shown in Table 6, only 35.4% of respondents recognize the scientific community's crucial role (score 5) in self-regulation. The majority rely heavily on publishers and institutions to police misconduct, failing to acknowledge their own professional duties. Furthermore, 21.9% consider existing integrity education to be completely ineffective.

Table 6. Full score distribution for each integrity measure

Measure	Mean Score	1 (%)	2 (%)	3 (%)	4 (%)	5 (%)
Strict investigation of integrity violations	4.34	5.0	2.6	9.6	19.0	63.9
Responsible review of publication process	4.09	6.1	4.8	13.4	25.5	50.2
Establish scientific evaluation & incentive systems	4.02	7.1	5.6	14.2	24.1	49.1
Utilize third-party monitoring platforms	3.90	8.0	5.9	18.3	23.8	44.1
Establish unified integrity standards	3.57	14.1	8.9	19.0	21.7	36.3
Strengthen self-regulation in scientific community	3.48	16.3	10.4	17.3	20.5	35.4
Regular integrity education courses	3.18	21.9	12.9	18.7	18.5	28.0

Note: Scores range from 1 (Almost no effect) to 5 (Very effective). Percentages may not sum to 100% due to rounding.

4. Scientometric tools and roles as a response

Bridging the perception-reality gap requires a comprehensive approach. Governance efforts must correct cognitive biases through evidence-based communication and deploy reliable analytical tools to secure the publication system. While effective governance requires a multi-stakeholder effort, this section specifically examines the positioning of scientometricians. Since modern academic fraud is industrialized, frontline researchers cannot bear the entire burden of verification. Scientometricians, equipped with data access and analytical skills, can significantly facilitate building these systemic defenses.

Following the governance framework proposed by Tang (2019), we suggest that scientometricians should adopt four active roles: building infrastructure, sounding fire alarms, conducting routine patrols, and facilitating knowledge dissemination. We translate these roles into practice through example tools or approaches.

4.1. Infrastructure: integrating and tracking questionable records

One of the primary roles of scientometricians is to provide foundational infrastructure. As our findings show, researchers frequently fail to verify their references. While organizations such as COPE have established retraction guidelines (COPE Council, 2025), the infrastructure for researchers to independently verify the integrity status of their references remains underdeveloped.

To fulfill this role, scientometricians should build comprehensive monitoring systems that integrate known misconduct cases. The AMEND platform (Li et al., 2024) and the Retraction Watch database³ may serve as practical examples. They aggregate retraction data, allowing institutions and authors to conveniently screen and verify the reliability of their references. By

³ <https://retractionwatch.com/>

providing a centralized point for inquiry, this infrastructure helps researchers avoid inadvertently citing retracted or flagged works throughout the research process.

4.2. Fire Alarm: issuing early warnings

The second role is acting as a rapid fire alarm. As misconduct shifts toward organized operations, traditional post-publication investigations are often too slow. Scientometricians should identify structural threats and issue warnings before the damage spreads.

For example, the Early Warning Journal List (EWL)⁴ demonstrates this proactive function. Instead of waiting for individual whistleblowers, the EWL uses bibliometric data to detect high-risk journals (e.g., journals with confirmed academic misconduct issue, abnormal publication patterns). By acting as an independent fire alarm and sharing these data-driven alerts, scientometricians can help trigger timely investigations.

4.3. Patrol: refining metrics for responsible evaluation

The third role involves conducting continuous patrols of the academic evaluation system. The underlying logic of academic misconduct is straightforward: if evaluation criteria reward gaming, gaming will persist. While scientometricians do not hold the administrative power to dictate institutional promotion policies, they are the professionals who develop and study evaluation metrics. Therefore, they have the expertise to continuously respond to emerging gaming behaviors and optimize these indicators.

Tools like the CAS Journal Ranking, continued as the XinRui Ranking since 2026⁵, put this patrol role into practice. This involves explicitly excluding citations generated by paper mills and detecting abnormal citation patterns. By systematically filtering out contaminated data, scientometricians help remove the structural rewards for misconduct and support a culture of responsible evaluation.

4.4. Knowledge brokering: acting as boundary-spanners across stakeholders

The final role is perhaps the most critical for closing the perception-reality gap. The scientific ecosystem consists of diverse stakeholders, including researchers, administrators, policy-makers, and publishers. They possess completely different discourse systems and understandings regarding integrity policies, evaluation rules, and the actual scale of misconduct.

To overcome this fragmentation, scientometricians should also act as boundary-spanners. Because they understand both the technical mechanics of publication databases and the practical needs of research evaluation, they are uniquely positioned to serve as knowledge brokers.

Rather than adopting a top-down educational approach, this role focuses on the interactive dissemination of research integrity knowledge across four key stakeholders. For researchers, it involves cultivating robust integrity principles and providing practical guidance on utilizing verification tools. For institutional administrators, it requires communicating nuanced perspectives, emphasizing that retractions should not be treated with simplistic, uniform judgments. For policy-makers, it means translating identified problems into actionable recommendations and advocating

⁴ <https://ewl.fenqubiao.com/>

⁵ <https://www.xr-scholar.com>

for the concepts of responsible research evaluation. Finally, for the publishers, it entails collaboratively sharing data on abnormal publication behaviors to enhance quality control and facilitate targeted investigations. By bridging these communication gaps, scientometricians facilitate a system-wide approach to integrity governance.

5. Discussion and Conclusions

Effective integrity governance requires accurately detecting the gap between the objective scale of misconduct and the research community's subjective perceptions. This baseline prevents blind interventions, clarifying whether the immediate priority is mitigating cognitive panic through communication or deploying technical safeguards against industrialized fraud.

Addressing this systemic crisis demands coordinated action across the entire knowledge production chain. For scientometricians, this means moving beyond descriptive citation analysis. By developing evidence-based tools, they actively embed themselves in governance, functioning as infrastructure builders, fire alarms, and metric optimizers. While the initial integration of these example tools into institutional workflows shows promising behavioral shifts, rigorous causal evaluations, including ongoing difference-in-differences (DID) analyses, are required to isolate their exact impact. Additionally, as our survey relies on a regional sample, future research should expand to diverse international samples.

As discussed frequently, safeguarding the scientific record requires breaking down traditional silos among researchers, publishers, and administrators. Equipped with data and analytical expertise, scientometricians are uniquely positioned to act as boundary-spanners. By translating evidence into practical tools, they facilitate the communication and coordination necessary for a unified defense against academic misconduct.

Open science practices

A companion report for this study can be accessed at https://drive.google.com/file/d/13sqsTRcvfft1Zdc53AFyuvy-vPWFcU3/view?usp=drive_link. Retraction data from public sources are available via the AMEND platform (<https://amend.fenqubiao.com/>). The survey instrument and aggregated responses are available upon request for replication. Evaluation methodologies are publicly documented. Specifically, the CAS Journal Ranking transitioned to the XinRui Journal Ranking (<https://www.xr-scholar.com/>) in 2026. The Early Warning Journal List (EWL, <https://ewl.fenqubiao.com/>), published annually from 2020 to 2025, was embedded into the ranking system in 2026. Under this integrated mechanism, high-risk journals are currently marked as "under review" and subject to continuous dynamic tracking.

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Author contributions

Sichao Tong: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing

Liying Yang: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision

Competing interests

Authors are the members of the CAS Journal Ranking, XinRui Journal Ranking and Early Warning Journal List team, which are mentioned as the example tools in this paper.

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